

RENEWABLE UZBEKISTAN IS IN DEVELOPMENT THE ROLE OF THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART

Raxmatullayev Nodirbek Farxod o'g'li

A student of the 3rd stage of production education in the field of art

Academic supervisor: Umid Todjidinov Todjidinovich

Senior lecturer of the "Culture and Art Management" department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11524070>

Abstract: This article discusses and describes the role of our national culture and art in the development of society in the development of Uzbekistan. In addition, opinions were expressed about the attention of our country to the sphere of culture and art.

Keywords: National culture and art, cultural heritage, innovative and integration processes, modern trends, concept, traditions.

ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫЙ УЗБЕКИСТАН НАХОДИТСЯ В РАЗВИТИИ РОЛЬ СФЕРЫ КУЛЬТУРЫ И ИСКУССТВА

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается и описывается роль нашей национальной культуры и искусства в развитии общества в развитии Узбекистана. Кроме того, были высказаны мнения о внимании нашей страны к сфере культуры и искусства.

Ключевые слова: Национальная культура и искусство, культурное наследие, инновационные и интеграционные процессы, современные тенденции, концепция, традиции.

INTRODUCTION

Today, every day is full of global changes. Updates, practical results of consistent reforms leave a bright mark on the pages of our life as a historical reality. In particular, the promising projects implemented in all fields during the next eight years, the large-scale creative works implemented in the localities are fundamentally changing not only the lifestyle and destiny of our people, but also the worldview. Innovative development of culture and art and attraction of modern trends (Russian, inclination, interest in something, striving for novelty) in the conditions of modernizing Uzbekistan remains one of the important issues that are gaining great relevance. Today's life also requires the development of new approaches to improving the quality of services provided to the population by cultural and art institutions. In the conditions of increasing general competition in all fields, the specific characteristics of culture and art present officials with serious tasks, such as the rational use of innovative methods of general management, and the improvement of the professional level of employees. At present, we all know that scientific and technical achievements are developing and reaching higher and higher heights. The comprehensive, universal, complex reality of culture and art requires them to be viewed harmoniously with all directions of social life and organized on this basis. But the ideological and educational influence of culture and art encourages to approach them as a separate spiritual phenomenon.

MAIN PART

If we look at the past, even though times change, useful ideas that serve people's interests forever have never been lost. For example, people's traditions, rituals, which lead to good, peaceful life, intangible cultural heritage of the people, even if they face pressures, they recognize that the people's desire will not be in vain. No matter how high the economy of a particular nation is, no matter how rich the country is, if it does not have spiritual culture, this country will be like a weak

castle built on sand. States and empires in history are clear examples of this. For the true development of the country, spiritual culture and economy must develop equally, and our compatriots in the field of culture are always trying to spread culture to our society and instill it in the minds of the young generation. Culture represents a unique form of human activity reflected in nature and interactions. The term culture is used in a broad sense and refers to the achievements of the society in production, social and spiritual life, education, education, intelligence and enlightenment, as well as the conditions that meet the human needs of life. represents the set. Therefore, culture and art are both a product of society and an indicator of quality.

In particular, our state has adopted more than 50 decisions, decrees, orders, regulatory legal documents on the development of the industry. For example, Decision PQ-3920 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 26, 2018 No. Decision No. PQ-4038 “On approving the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, on May 26, 2020, “Measures to further increase the role and influence of culture and art in the life of society” Presidential Decree No. PF-6000 dated January 9, 2019 “On Fundamental Improvement of the System of Raising Legal Awareness and Legal Culture in Society” dated December 9, 2021 “Culture and PQ-36 on the further improvement of the support system for the development of art” and on February 2, 2022 “Additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art” Law No. PQ-112, adopted by the Legislative Chamber on January 20, 2021, Law No. ORQ-668 “On Cultural Activities and Cultural Organizations” also defines current issues related to the field.

In particular, on November 28, 2018, the decision No. PQ-4038 “On approving the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan” defined the following as the main tasks of our national culture and art in our country;

- ❖ further improvement of the legal framework related to the field of culture, the institutional system in this field and the activities of cultural and art institutions;
- ❖ preservation of our historical and cultural heritage and its wide application in the education of the young generation;
- ❖ inculcating national and universal values in the minds of our youth, preserving ethnic cultural traditions and supporting national creativity on this basis;
- ❖ creation and expansion of the necessary conditions for the realization of the creative potential of the population, including the youth;
- ❖ wide introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the field of culture, effective use of innovative ideas and technologies in further research and promotion of culture;
- ❖ ensuring active participation of citizens, including persons with disabilities, in cultural life and social equality in the use of cultural services;
- ❖ organization and development of mutually effective international relations in the cultural sphere, viewing national culture as an integral part of world culture, paying special attention to equality and respect for human rights in this regard;
- ❖ ensure that the decisions made in the economic, social and cultural spheres are consistent with the unified state policy in this sphere;
- ❖ to ensure the full functioning of cultural and art institutions, to further strengthen their material resource base, to establish public control over the preservation and protection of objects.

Cultural and public events are being held by the Ministry of Culture in order to promote the culture and art of Uzbekistan in other countries, to create a positive image of Uzbek national art and culture. In particular, 6 offline and 10 online cultural events in foreign countries in 2021, 28 cultural events in 2022, 43 cultural events and conferences in 2023, 21 cultural and public events until today in 2024, including days of culture, etc. gazmas, concert-show programs were organized.

The work carried out in the direction of the development of culture and art in our country is extremely consistent with the priority measures aimed at ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new level, reflected in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan. We can say that these reforms will contribute to the practical realization of the idea "From the strategy of actions to the strategy of development" based on the principle of goodness and humanity, and the implementation of the concept of "New Uzbekistan – an enlightened society". Each nation occupies a strong place in world civilization with the power of its culture and art. The development of this sector is one of the important factors that show the strength and potential of the country, the value of the people, its reputation and status in the world.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, today the restoration of the huge, priceless spiritual and cultural heritage created by our ancestors over many centuries has risen to the level of state policy. After gaining independence, the leadership of Uzbekistan, first of all, taking into account the needs and wishes of our people, paid great attention to the restoration of ancient holidays and the formation of new independence holidays. In the years of independence, the material and technical base of national cinema, theater, and museum art was strengthened, through which the past and history can be seen, remembered, sensed, studied, and therefore the process of revival and development of Uzbek national creativity is accelerated. was carried out in stages. Also, "O'zbekiston tarixi", "Madaniyat va ma'rifat", and "Navo" television channels were launched in order to convey the history, culture and art of our country to the masses, to create awareness among our youth. To date, we have strengthened our efforts to carry out such noble works, to develop culture and art, and to glorify this field to the whole world. All the cultural reforms carried out in our republic serve the future of man, the spirituality of the youth of our country, the preservation of our national culture and art, and its constant promotion.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "O'zbekiston Respublikasida milliy madaniyatni yanada rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risida"gi 2018-yil 28-noyabrdagi PQ-4038-sonli qarori.
2. Haydarov. Madaniyat va san'at muassasalari faoliyatini tashkil etishda innovatsion yondashuvlar konferensiya to'plami. Toshkent – 2020. 14-15 betlar.
3. Haydarov. Madaniyat – milliy yuksalish poydevori. – Toshkent: Oltin meros press. 2021. – B. 478.
4. O.A.Nazarbekov. Yuksak e'tibor va ehtirom bizga kuch, shijoat beradi. Xalq so'zi gazetasi. Toshkent-2022. 4-B.
5. S. To'ychiyeva. Madaniyat va san'atimiz rivojidadagi zarsahifalar. Yangi O'zbekiston gazetasi. Toshkent-2022.
6. Haydarov. Milliy madaniyat renessans poydevori. Yangi O'zbekiston gazetasi. Toshkent-2020. 6-B.

7. N. Mahmudov. Xalqimiz ma'naviy olamini yanada yuksaltirishning mustahkam poydevori // Yangi O'zbekiston gazetasi. Toshkent-2022. 6-B.
8. Todjidinovich T. U. PRODYUSERLIK FAOLIYATINING KELIB CHIQISHI VA RIVOJLANISHI //Research Focus International Scientific Journal. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 252-257.
9. Todjidinov U. T. MADANIYAT VA SAN 'AT BOSHQARUVINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI: MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR //Oriental Art and Culture. – 2023. – T. 4. – №. 1. – C. 301-306.
10. Todjidinov U. T. MADANIYAT VA SAN 'AT MENEJMENTI VA UNING ZAMONAVIY KO 'RINISHLARI //Oriental Art and Culture. – 2023. – T. 4. – №. 1. – C. 307-315.
11. Todjidinov U. T. SHOU BIZNESDA PRODYUSERLIK KASBINING O 'RNI //Oriental Art and Culture. – 2023. – T. 4. – №. 1. – C. 529-537.